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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce a new method to implement chaotic generators based on Henon map chaotic system given by the state equations by using Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA). The aim of this method is to increase the frequency of the chaotic generators. The new method is based on MATLAB® Software, Xilinx System Generator, Xilinx Alliance tools, Leonardo spectrum or Synplicity Synplify and ModelSim XE PLUSE. The toolbox of the Xilinx System Generator used as toolbox under the MATLAB® Simulink toolbox to convert any MATLAB® Simulink model to the Xilinx System Generator model then to generate the VHDL code for that model. The hardware can be used directly in chaotic communication systems with high frequencies.

Keywords: Chaotic, Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA), Communications systems.

INTRODUCTION

The Xilinx System Generator bridges the gap between conceptual architectural design and the actual implementation in a Xilinx field programmable Gate Array (FPGA). The field programmable Gate Array (FPGA) is a type of programmable device. Programmable devices are a class of general-purpose chips that can be configured for a wide variety of applications. They have the capability of implementing the logic of not only hundreds but also thousands of discrete devices. The System Generator for Simulink, developed in partnership with The Math Works, Inc enables to develop high-performance DSP systems for Xilinx FPGAs using the popular MATLAB® /Simulink products from The MathWorks, Inc (Marchand,1999) . As a plug-in to the Simulink modeling software, the Xilinx System Generator provides a bit-accurate model of FPGA circuits, and automatically generates a synthesizable Hardware Description Language (VHDL) code and a testbench. This VHDL design can then be synthesized for implementation in Xilinx Virtex®-II, Virtex, and Spartan®-II FPGAs. The Xilinx Blockset enables bit-true and cycle-true modeling, with Xilinx FPGA hardware as the target. It includes parametric blocks for DSP, arithmetic, and logic functions like FFTs, FIR Filters, Multipliers, Memories, and gateway blocks to communicate with the MATLAB® environment, where you also have access to the extensive set of Simulink libraries (The MathWorks and Xilinx Plans web page: <http://www.mathworks.com/company/pressroom/index.shtml>)

But why we used FPGA instead of analogue circuit? The answer is, Analogue chaotic generators have been used for communication systems (Matsumoto 1987). Recovery of the information signal depends on how well the receiver is synchronised with the transmitter. This requires that the parameters of both receiver and transmitter be matched to a high degree of accuracy. This requirement is difficult to achieve in analogue systems especially that the values of analogue circuit component are functions of age and temperature. The most obvious solution is to implement the generators using digital hardware. The generators are first represented by a set of non-linear equations and a system-based model is developed to represent these equations directly. The FPGA overcomes that entire problem and in the same time we can get high frequency. Once the VHDL code is generated and synthesized then the netlist file will produce, through the Xilinx Alliance tools the bit file will produce. Once the bit file is available, the impact software under the Xilinx Alliance tools will use it to download the bit file to target FPGA device. By this way we can control the frequency of the chaotic signal during the FPGA device by using clock, so that the frequency of the chaotic signal depends on the frequency of the clock for the FPGA device. The main thing which is the output from the FPGA device is digital. To see the analogue output we need Digital to analogue (D/A) converter device. In this case the frequency of the system depends on the clock sampling rate and the sampling rate of the D/A device and the numbers of D/A bits. The presented method is depended on the Xilinx System, which convert the Simulink model from MATLAB® to VHDL code.

Fig. 2: The Henon map chaotic generator attractor.

Fig. 3: The Henon map chaotic generator spectrum.

Now, convert the model, which was shown in Fig.1 to Xilinx System Generator Model using the Xilinx Blockset under the MATLAB®.

To make synchronization for the Henon map chaotic generator blocks, all the number of bits equals 32 and binary of points equal 18 as shown in Fig. 4. The stop time was chosen as $10^3 \times dt$ and the fixed step size as dt where $dt=10^{-2}$. Fig. 5 shows the attractor result of the simulation model of the Henon map chaotic generator.

Fig.4: The Henon map chaotic generator model using the Xilinx System Generator.

Fig. 5: The Henon map chaotic generator attractor.

Comparing this result with the result from MATLAB[®] Simulink including the delay in the system it's the same. Fig. 6 shows the spectrum of Xilinx Henon map Generator, which depends on the values of step size of the model dt.

Fig. 6: The Henon map chaotic generator spectrum.

To increase the frequency of the Henon map generator system the value of dt was reducing and adding another CMult block with value $10^{-2}/dt$ to control the frequency, dt was reducing up to 5×10^{-6} .

Now, System generator block was used to generate the VHDL code for the Henon map system. The ModelSim SE Plus Software was used to compiling the VHDL code and simulates it by using two files VCOM and VSIM, which was generated already from the Xilinx System Generator. Fig. 7 shows the simulation results of VHDL Henon map Code using the ModelSim as in the Hardware results.

Fig. 7: The Henon map chaotic generator results by ModelSim.

The ModelSim Simulation is used to know what should be the results from the Xilinx System Generator in the Hardware comparing with the MATLAB® simulation results. We require the synthesis tools either Leonardo Spectrum (The Leonardo Spectrum web page: <http://www.mentor.com/synthesis/leonardospectrum/>) or Synplicity's Synplify (The Synplicity's Synplify web page: <http://www.synplicity.com/>) to synthesis the code. This will produce netlist file, which must be put as input through the back end of the Xilinx Alliance tools Xilinx Alliance tools web page: http://www.xilinx.com/xlnx/xil_prodcat_landingpage.jsp?title=ISE+Alliance. This tool will then generate a bitstream file that can then be downloaded on the FPGA by using parallel port cable, which is connected to the FPGA device Board.

CONCLUSION

A new method to design chaotic generator models in real time is introduced which is capable of implementing the chaotic systems that are given by state equations in real time using Filed Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) system. The method is implemented by MATLAB®, SIMULINK, Xilinx System Generator, Xilinx Alliance tools, Leonardo spectrum or Synplicity Synplify and ModelSim XE PLUSE. A clock time dt (the simulation step size) to control the frequency band is used in this type of chaotic generator. The method is useful to implement the chaotic generators at high frequencies which depends on the clock of the simulation of the model itself. Both continuous and discrete chaotic generators can be implemented even if the system cannot be represented by a physical electronic circuit. Modification of any system is a simple change in the block diagram or the parameter values within the block.

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